

Hierarchical Geometric Sliding-Mode Control for Trajectory Tracking of Connected Multibody Systems on $SO(3) \times \mathcal{S}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^3$

Atiyeh Karimi Pour
School of Mechanical Engineering
University of Tehran
 Tehran, Iran
 atiyeh.karimipour@ut.ac.ir

Moosa Ayati
School of Mechanical Engineering
University of Tehran
 Tehran, Iran
 m.ayati@ut.ac.ir

Mohammad Reza Zakerzadeh
School of Mechanical Engineering
University of Tehran
 Tehran, Iran
 zakerzadeh@ut.ac.ir

Abstract—We design a hierarchical terminal sliding-mode controller (TSMC) for a tethered rigid-body-point-mass system. The plant is decomposed into (i) translation in \mathbb{R}^3 , (ii) a direction subsystem on \mathcal{S}^2 (with an \mathcal{S}^3 lift used to synthesize a virtual control), and (iii) rigid-body attitude on $SO(3)$. Using the tangent-bundle group operation, we construct intrinsic sliding laws on the Lie groups; the resulting error maps are curvature-consistent, and the zero set $\{s = 0\} \subset TG$ is a forward-invariant Lie subgroup. The Euclidean part uses a standard TSMC. We establish finite reaching and (almost) global tracking for each subsystem. The overall cascade is validated in simulation, showing improved tracking and disturbance rejection over PD+feedforward.

Index Terms—Terminal sliding-mode control, Geometric control, Lie groups, Tethered systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Sliding-mode control (SMC) is a robust design framework for nonlinear plants subject to matched disturbances. One selects a sliding variable $s(x, t)$ so that the reduced dynamics on the set $\{s = 0\}$ are (asymptotically or finite-time) stable, then prescribes a reaching law that drives trajectories to $\{s = 0\}$ in finite time and renders it forward invariant.

Following the foundational formulation by Utkin [1], several variants address classical SMC drawbacks such as chattering and relative-degree limitations: higher-order and super-twisting SMC achieve continuous control for relative degree one under matched, Lipschitz disturbances [2]; integral SMC eliminates the reaching phase sensitivity by embedding the disturbance estimate in the sliding variable [3]. Terminal SMC [4] designs a nonlinear sliding manifold (typically via fractional powers) that renders the reduced dynamics finite-time stable. In this work we adopt finite-time sliding laws at each subsystem.

We focus on designing TSMC specifically for mechanical systems. Many mechanical systems combine translation and rotation, so their natural state is (g, ν) with configuration g on a curved manifold (e.g., $SO(3)$ or \mathcal{S}^3) and body velocity ν in the associated Lie algebra. In

purely translational cases ($G = \mathbb{R}^3$), conventional terminal SMC uses linear, Euclidean sliding surfaces (e.g., $s = e_v + \lambda|e_x|^{p/q}\text{sgn}(e_x)$). For rotational motion this is not appropriate: configuration is not a vector, global coordinates do not exist (Euler angles are singular, quaternions double-cover $SO(3)$), and linear mixing of g and ν breaks invariance and can cause unwinding. The remedy is to define sliding laws intrinsically on the Lie group: build an invariant configuration error ($g_e \in G$), map it into the algebra via a logarithmic map, and couple it with the velocity error to form $s \in \mathfrak{g}$. This keeps the design coordinate-free, respects the manifold’s curvature, and yields globally meaningful tracking behavior.

We study a tethered rigid-body-point-mass system: a rigid body connected to a point mass by a massless, inextensible tether. Our goal is to track a prescribed trajectory of the end mass in the presence of matched disturbances, using a hierarchical terminal SMC design. This model captures key features of crane load handling, aerial load transport (e.g., quadrotors with suspended payloads), and on-orbit tethered capture, while remaining simple enough to expose the core geometric control issues.

Related work on tethered payload systems spans flatness-based design, geometric control, and sliding modes. Tang [5] derives the dynamics via virtual work, shows differential flatness, and implements a PD law for a simplified 2-D case. Sreenath et al. [6] propose a PD+feedforward controller to track the payload trajectory, with a singular-perturbation argument for stability; robustness to matched disturbances is not addressed. Yu et al. [7] develop a backstepping controller that depends on an accurate model, leaving disturbance rejection uncertain. To mitigate swing, Yang et al. [8] use a hierarchical SMC with super-twisting on separated translational/rotational channels; other SMC approaches [9], [10] similarly focus on swing attenuation rather than full trajectory tracking. In contrast, we target *trajectory tracking* of the end mass under matched disturbances via a geometric, Lie-group TSMC architecture.

We employ a three-stage hierarchical design to track the

end-mass trajectory. The plant is decomposed into: (i) a translation subsystem in \mathbb{R}^3 ; (ii) a direction subsystem on \mathcal{S}^2 (with an \mathcal{S}^3 lift only to synthesize a virtual control); and (iii) rigid-body attitude on $SO(3)$. In stage (i), with the tether direction and the rigid body attitude treated as frozen, we design a terminal sliding surface on the mass position/velocity errors and compute, as a virtual input, the commanded force component parallel to the desired tether direction, f_{\parallel} . The resulting direction then serves as the reference for stage (ii).

In stage (ii), the tether endpoint is fixed and the rigid-body attitude held constant. The reduced state is the tether direction $\xi \in \mathcal{S}^2$ with kinematics $\dot{\xi} = \omega \times \xi$, $\omega \in T_{\xi}\mathcal{S}^2$. Since Euclidean TSMC is inapplicable, we adopt the following intrinsic formulation: the direction error is lifted to the unit-quaternion group \mathcal{S}^3 , mapped through the shortest-arc rotation [11], and projected back to the tangent space to define the sliding variable in $T\mathcal{S}^3$. A reaching law ensures finite convergence to the manifold, while the terminal term yields finite-time decay of the residual error. The resulting virtual input is the commanded lateral force f_{\perp} , the component orthogonal to ξ , passed to the attitude stage.

In stage (iii), we analyze the rigid-body attitude. With the tether and end mass held fixed, the rigid body undergoes pure rotation. Attitude evolves on $SO(3)$ with angular velocity in its Lie algebra. We adopt the same intrinsic sliding construction as above, i.e. built on invariant attitude and velocity errors, so the sliding variable that lives in the algebra, is coordinate-free, and avoids unwinding. A reaching law provides finite approach to the sliding set, while the terminal manifold shapes the reduced error. This stage tracks the desired attitude generated upstream (to realize f_{\parallel} , f_{\perp} , and the commanded tether direction) and delivers the actual control torque.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews kinematics and dynamics on Lie groups, fixes notation, and recalls the tangent-bundle group operation and sliding subgroup following [11]. Section III presents the plant and the hierarchical architecture. Sections IV, V, and VI treat the three subsystems (translation in \mathbb{R}^3 ; direction on \mathcal{S}^2 with an \mathcal{S}^3 lift; attitude on $SO(3)$). Section VII reports simulation results, and Section VIII concludes ¹

II. PRELIMINARIES

A Lie group G is a group that is also a smooth manifold whose multiplication and inversion maps are smooth. Classic examples include the general linear group $GL(2, \mathbb{R})$ and the rotation group $SO(3)$. For any point $x \in G$, the tangent space T_xG is the vector space of velocities of smooth curves through x .

The identity element is $e \in G$ with $eg = ge = g$ for all $g \in G$. The tangent space at the identity, T_eG , is

¹Code and videos: <https://github.com/a-karimipour/Sliding-Mode-Control-of-a-Tethered-Rigid-Body-Mass-Point-System>.

the Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} . It is a vector space equipped with the Lie bracket $[\cdot, \cdot] : \mathfrak{g} \times \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$, a bilinear, antisymmetric map satisfying the Jacobi identity. We use \mathfrak{g} for algebra elements and write $\text{Ad}_g : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$ and $\text{ad}_{\xi}\zeta = [\xi, \zeta]$ for the adjoint and its differential when needed.

A. Mechanical systems on Lie groups

Let G be a Lie group with identity e , Lie algebra $\mathfrak{g} = T_eG$, and left-invariant Riemannian metric induced by an inertia operator $\mathbb{I} : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}^*$ (an inner product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_{\mathfrak{g}}$). We write the flat/sharp maps as $\mathbb{I}^{\flat} : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}^*$ and $\mathbb{I}^{\sharp} : \mathfrak{g}^* \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$. The adjoint operators are $\text{ad}_{\xi}\zeta = [\xi, \zeta]$ and $\langle \text{ad}_{\xi}^*\mu, \zeta \rangle = \langle \mu, [\zeta, \xi] \rangle$.

A left-trivialized mechanical system has configuration $g(t) \in G$ and body velocity $\nu(t) \in \mathfrak{g}$ with kinematics and dynamics

$$\dot{g} = g\nu, \quad (1a)$$

$$\dot{\nu} + \nabla_{\nu}^{\mathfrak{g}}\nu = f_u + \delta_d, \quad (1b)$$

where $\nabla^{\mathfrak{g}}$ is the Levi-Civita connection associated with \mathbb{I} , and

$$\nabla_{\xi}^{\mathfrak{g}}\zeta = \frac{1}{2}[\xi, \zeta] - \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{I}^{\sharp}(\text{ad}_{\xi}^*\mathbb{I}^{\flat}\zeta + \text{ad}_{\zeta}^*\mathbb{I}^{\flat}\xi). \quad (2)$$

Equation (1b) is the Euler–Poincaré form; in Euclidean spaces (flat metric and abelian algebra) the connection term vanishes. The input and disturbance are modeled as

$$f_u = \sum_{a=1}^m u^a(t)\mathbb{I}^{\sharp}f^a, \quad \delta_d \in \mathfrak{g},$$

with $u^a \in \mathbb{R}$ and fixed covectors $f^a \in \mathfrak{g}^*$ specifying the input directions (matched disturbances enter through the same channel). Thus a system on G is characterized by (G, \mathbb{I}) and the generalized forces $f_u + \delta_d$.

B. Sliding Subgroup

In mechanical systems on Lie groups the state is $(g, \nu) \in TG$: the configuration g lives on the manifold G while the body velocity ν lives in a tangent space. A Euclidean sliding surface (a linear constraint in coordinates) cannot capture this geometry globally. The remedy is to define the sliding law on the tangent bundle TG , so that the manifold part (configuration) and the linear part (algebra/velocity) are handled jointly and in a coordinate-free way.

The tangent bundle collects all tangent spaces: $TG = \{(g, \nu) \mid g \in G, \nu \in T_gG\}$, and itself forms a smooth manifold. Via left translation, each T_gG is identified with $T_eG = \mathfrak{g}$, so we will use the left-trivialized form $TG \simeq G \times \mathfrak{g}$. Our sliding set will therefore be defined as a subset $S \subset TG$, so it constrains configuration and body velocity jointly.

To construct a sliding law on TG , we endow $TG \simeq G \times \mathfrak{g}$ with a group operation (following [11]). For $\lambda > 0$ and a kinematic map $\nu_u : G \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$,

$$\begin{aligned} (g_1, \nu_1) \star (g_2, \nu_2) = \\ (g_1g_2, \nu_1 + \nu_2 + \lambda\nu_u(g_1) + \lambda\nu_u(g_2) - \lambda\nu_u(g_1g_2)). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Assume ν_u satisfies: (i) $\nu_u(e) = 0$; (ii) $\nu_u(g^{-1}) = -\nu_u(g)$; and (iii) there exists a smooth Morse function $V : G \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ with a strict minimum at e such that along $\dot{g} = g\nu_u(g)$ we have $\dot{V}(g) < 0$ away from a negligible set and, locally near e , $\dot{V}(g) \leq -y(g)V(g)$ with $y(g) > 0$.

Under these conditions, (TG, \star) is a Lie group with identity $(e, 0)$ and inverse $(g, \nu)^{-1} = (g^{-1}, -\nu)$. This structure lets us define sliding sets intrinsically on TG and later prove their invariance using compact Lyapunov arguments.

Define the sliding map $s : TG \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$ by $s(g, \nu) = \nu + \lambda\nu_u(g)$. The sliding set

$$H := \{(g, \nu) \in TG \mid s(g, \nu) = 0\}$$

is a Lie subgroup of (TG, \star) (identity $(e, 0)$, closure, inverse) under the operation in (3) (cf. [11]).

Moreover, H is forward invariant: on H , $\nu = -\lambda\nu_u(g)$, so $\dot{g} = g\nu = -\lambda g\nu_u(g)$, and, by the Morse property of ν_u ,

$$\dot{V}(g) = \langle dV(g), -\lambda g\nu_u(g) \rangle < 0 \quad (4)$$

away from the negligible set. Hence, trajectories that reach H remain on it.

C. Invariant errors and the sliding law on TG

To respect the geometry of G , tracking errors are defined intrinsically. Let $g_r(t) \in G$ and $\nu_r(t) \in \mathfrak{g}$ be the reference. The configuration and body-velocity errors are

$$g_e := g_r^{-1}g, \quad (5a)$$

$$\nu_e := \nu - \text{Ad}_{g_e^{-1}}\nu_r, \quad (5b)$$

so that $g_e = e$ and $\nu_e = 0$ at perfect tracking. For later use set $\eta_r := \text{Ad}_{g_e^{-1}}\nu_r$.

With the kinematic map $\nu_u : G \rightarrow \mathfrak{g}$ (cf. Sec. II-B), define the sliding variable on the error state $h_e = (g_e, \nu_e) \in TG$ by

$$s(h_e) = \nu_e + \lambda\nu_u(g_e) \in \mathfrak{g}. \quad (6)$$

The set $\{s = 0\} \subset TG$ is the sliding subgroup from Sec. II-B. On $s = 0$ the reduced error dynamics are first order on G and decrease the Morse function associated with ν_u .

For controller synthesis it is convenient to differentiate s along the closed-loop flow. Using (1)–(2) one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_s s &= \dot{\nu}_e + \lambda\dot{\nu}_u(g_e) - \mathbb{I}^\sharp(\text{ad}_s^* \mathbb{I}^\flat s) \\ &= f_u - \nabla_{\nu}^{\mathfrak{g}} \nu + \lambda\dot{\nu}_u(g_e) - \mathbb{I}^\sharp(\text{ad}_s^* \mathbb{I}^\flat s), \end{aligned}$$

and, after substituting the Euler–Poincaré term and rearranging, the nominal *equivalent control* that enforces $\nabla_s s = 0$ is

$$f_u^{\text{eq}} = \mathbb{I}^\sharp\left(\text{ad}_{\lambda\nu_u(g_e) - \eta_r}^* \mathbb{I}^\flat \nu\right) - \lambda\dot{\nu}_u(g_e) + \dot{\eta}_r. \quad (7)$$

With the Lyapunov function $V_s : TG \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as $V_s = 1/2\mathbb{I}(s, s)$, adding a damping term $-Ks$ to (7) yields $\dot{V}_s = -2K V_s$ in the nominal model.

Fig. 1: Tethered point-mass-rigid-body system and associated dynamics.

Remark 1. In implementation, we use a continuous reaching law of the form $u_s = -Ks$ to damp oscillations, together with a discontinuous term that guarantees finite-time convergence. Consequently, the trajectories reach the sliding set in finite time even under matched disturbances. Moreover, the terminal manifold ensures finite-time convergence of the reduced dynamics once $s = 0$ is reached.

III. MULTIBODY SYSTEMS ON $SO(3) \times \mathcal{S}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^3$

We consider a multibody system comprising a six-DOF rigid body connected to a point mass by a massless, inextensible tether of fixed length. Figure 1 depicts the geometry and the resulting equations of motion: the rigid-body attitude evolves on $SO(3)$, the tether direction on \mathcal{S}^2 , and the point-mass translation in \mathbb{R}^3 . The real control inputs are the thrust magnitude f (along the rigid body's third axis) and the rigid body torque M .

As in (8), the state splits into translation $(x, v) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3$ for the point mass, direction $(\xi, \omega) \in \mathcal{S}^2 \times T_\xi \mathcal{S}^2$ for the tether, and attitude $(R, \Omega) \in SO(3) \times \mathbb{R}^3$ for the rigid body, all expressed in the inertial frame. The control inputs are thrust magnitude $f \in \mathbb{R}$ (along $R e_3$) and body torque $M \in \mathbb{R}^3$. e_3 is the unit vector along the z -axis. Physical parameters are the rigid-body mass m_R , inertia matrix J_R , point mass m_P , tether length l , and gravity g . The system is (under standard assumptions) differentially flat [5] with flat outputs (x, ψ) (point-mass position and yaw), so desired state and input trajectories can be synthesized from x_r , a yaw profile ψ_r , and their derivatives; we exploit this to generate references for the cascade.

Our objective is to track a prescribed point-mass trajectory (x_r) using a hierarchical terminal SMC. We decompose the plant into three subsystems and assign each a terminal sliding law with continuous and discontinuous reaching terms, producing virtual inputs that cascade downstream. The first stage commands the desired tether direction and along-tether force; the second regulates the

Fig. 2: System decomposition into point mass, pendulum, and rigid body.

tether direction on \mathcal{S}^2 and outputs a lateral force; the third orients the rigid body on $SO(3)$ to realize the required thrust direction and torque. The structure is:

- (i) *Point mass* (Fig. 2a; (8c)). Using x_r and $v_r = \dot{x}_r$, we design a terminal surface in \mathbb{R}^3 . The virtual output is the *along-tether force component* (f_{\parallel}) (the component of fRe_3 parallel to the tether direction ξ), and the associated *desired direction* (ξ_d) to be tracked by stage (ii).
- (ii) *Direction on \mathcal{S}^2* (Fig. 2b; (8b)). With the mass point fixed, we regulate the tether direction to ξ_d using the intrinsic $\mathcal{S}^2/\mathcal{S}^3$ -lift sliding law. The virtual output is the *lateral force* (f_{\perp}) (the component of fRe_3 orthogonal to ξ), chosen so that (ξ) and (ω) track (ξ_d) and (ω_r) (with ω_r from flatness).
- (iii) *Thrust vector and attitude target*. Combining the two components yields the *desired thrust vector* $F_d := f_{\parallel} + f_{\perp}$ (parallel + lateral). The component of F_d along the current rigid-body z -axis, i.e., $f = F_d \cdot (Re_3)$, and its direction $F_d/\|F_d\|$ define the thrust command and the attitude target for the rigid body (with yaw ψ_r as specified).
- (iv) *Rigid body* (Fig. 2c; (8a)). We apply the $SO(3)$ geometric sliding law to track the desired attitude (R_d) (constructed from $F_d/\|F_d\|$ and ψ_r) and angular rate (Ω_r) (from flatness), delivering the *actual torque* (M).

The control structure is summarized in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Hierarchical sliding-mode control structure with three layers.

In the next section, we investigate each subsystem separately and derive the corresponding sliding laws.

IV. TSMC FOR \mathbb{R}^3 SUBSYSTEM

The point mass evolves in Euclidean space, so we use a classical terminal surface with a reaching law that contains a continuous and a discontinuous robust term.

Let $e_x := x - x_r$ and $e_v := v - v_r$. Define (component-wise)

$$s_P = e_v + \lambda_P |e_x|^{\frac{p_P}{q_P}} \odot \text{sign}(e_x), \quad 0 < \frac{p_P}{q_P} < 1, \lambda_P > 0.$$

Use the reaching law

$$\dot{s}_P = -K_P s_P - \rho_P \frac{s_P}{\|s_P\| + \varepsilon},$$

with $K_P > 0$, and the small $\varepsilon > 0$ that prevents numerical division by zero and recovers the hard sign function as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ (Filippov sense). From

$$\dot{v} = \frac{1}{m_R + m_P} (f_{\parallel} - m_R l \|\dot{\xi}\|^2 \xi) - g e_3, \quad \dot{e}_v = \dot{v} - a_r, \quad a_r := \dot{v}_r,$$

differentiating s_P yields the pre-projection (f'_{\parallel}) command

$$f'_{\parallel} = f_{\parallel}^{\text{eq}} + (m_R + m_P) \left(-K_P s_P - \rho_P \frac{s_P}{\|s_P\| + \varepsilon} \right) \quad (9)$$

where

$$f_{\parallel}^{\text{eq}} = (m_R + m_P) \left(g e_3 + a_r - \lambda_P \frac{p_P}{q_P} |e_x|^{\frac{p_P}{q_P} - 1} \odot e_v \right) + m_R l \|\dot{\xi}\|^2 \xi.$$

Let $m := m_R + m_P$ and assume the disturbance entering the same channel as the thrust is shown by $d_T(t)$ is bounded as $\|d_T(t)\| \leq \Delta_T$. Then, with $V = \frac{1}{2} \|s_P\|^2$ and f'_{\parallel} , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V} &= -s_P^{\top} K_P s_P - \frac{\rho_P}{m} \|s_P\| + \frac{1}{m} |d_T| \|s_P\| \\ &\leq -\lambda_{\min}(K_P) \|s_P\|^2 - \frac{\rho_P - \Delta_T}{m} \|s_P\|. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, if $\rho_P > \Delta_T$, then s_P reaches 0 in finite time despite the matched disturbance; hence $s_P \rightarrow 0$. A conservative reaching time bound is $T_{\text{reach}} \leq \frac{m}{\rho_P - \Delta_T} |s_P(0)|$.

Practical note. The factor $|e_x|^{\frac{p_P}{q_P} - 1}$ is unbounded at $e_x = 0$; we use a small regularization $(|e_x| + \varepsilon)^{\frac{p_P}{q_P} - 1}$ with $\varepsilon \ll 1$ for numerical robustness.

V. TSMC FOR \mathcal{S}^2 SUBSYSTEM

The direction subsystem regulates the tether direction $\xi \in \mathcal{S}^2$ using an \mathcal{S}^3 lift to construct curvature-consistent errors. Let $q \in \mathcal{S}^3$ be the unit quaternion that maps a fixed ξ_0 to ξ along the shortest arc, and let q_r be the quaternion that maps ξ_0 to the desired direction $\xi_d := f'_{\parallel} / \|f'_{\parallel}\|$, where f'_{\parallel} is defined in (9) but with the discontinuity term removed, so that this discontinuity appears only in the actuation channel and not in the desired tether direction. Define the configuration/velocity errors on the lift

$$q_e = q_r^{-1} \otimes q, \quad \bar{\omega}_e = \bar{\omega} - \text{Ad}_{q_e^{-1}} \bar{\omega}_r \in \mathfrak{s}^3 \simeq \mathbb{R}^3,$$

($\cdot := \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathfrak{s}^3$), and the logarithmic error $\omega_u := \log(q_e) \in \mathfrak{s}^3 \simeq \mathbb{R}^3$ (the quaternion logarithm, i.e., shortest-arc rotation vector). Define the intrinsic sliding variable

$$s_T = \omega_e + \lambda_T |\omega_u|^{\frac{p_T}{q_T}} \odot \text{sign}(\omega_u) \in T_\xi \mathcal{S}^2.$$

with $0 < \frac{p_T}{q_T} < 1$, $\lambda_T > 0$ (componentwise power/sign on the algebra vector).

Specializing (7) to \mathcal{S}^3 with inertia $J_T = m_R l^2 I$ and using the identifications $\mathfrak{s}^3 \simeq \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\text{ad}_\zeta \eta = \zeta \times \eta$, a compact equivalent control is

$$\alpha^{\text{eq}} = J_T^{-1} ((J_T \omega) \times (\lambda_T \omega_u - \eta_T)) - \lambda_T \dot{\omega}_u + \dot{\eta}_T,$$

where $\eta_T := \text{Ad}_{q_e^{-1}} \omega_r$.

From (8b), the input to this stage is the lateral force vector $f_\perp := \xi \times f R e_3 \in T_\xi \mathcal{S}^2$.

To handle matched disturbance d_T and guarantee reaching, augment α_T^{eq} with a continuous damping and a discontinuous bump in the tangent plane:

$$\alpha_T = \alpha_T^{\text{eq}} - K_T s_T - \rho_T \frac{s_T}{\|s_T\| + \varepsilon},$$

where $K_T \succ 0$, $\rho_T > 0$, and $\varepsilon > 0$. The commanded lateral force is

$$f_\perp = -m_R l \xi \times \alpha_T.$$

Let $V_T = \frac{1}{2} \|s_T\|^2$ and having $\|d_T\| \leq \Delta_T$. Then

$$\dot{s}_T = -K_T s_T - \rho_T \frac{s_T}{\|s_T\| + \varepsilon} + \frac{1}{m_R l} d_T,$$

so

$$\dot{V}_T \leq -\lambda_{\min}(K_T) \|s_T\|^2 - \left(\rho_T - \frac{\Delta_T}{m_R l} \right) \|s_T\|.$$

Thus, if $\rho_T > \Delta_T / (m_R l)$, s_T reaches 0 in finite time and remains there. A conservative bound is $T_{\text{reach}} \leq \frac{m_R l}{\rho_T - \Delta_T} \|s_T(0)\|$. On $s_T = 0$, the reduced dynamics yield finite-time decay of the geodesic error via the terminal term.

This f_\perp is the virtual output passed to the attitude stage. Together with the along-tether component from stage (i), namely

$$f_\parallel = \xi^\top f'_\parallel \xi, \quad (10)$$

(since only the along-tether component is actuated [6]), it produces the thrust vector $F_d = f_\parallel + F_\perp$ [7].

VI. TSMC FOR THE $SO(3)$ SUBSYSTEM

This stage orients the rigid body so that its body z -axis aligns with the thrust vector $F_d = f_\parallel + f_\perp$ while respecting a desired yaw ψ_r .

Let $b_3 := F_d / \|F_d\|$. Choose $b_{1,\text{proj}} := (I - b_3 b_3^\top) e_1$; if $\|b_{1,\text{proj}}\|$ is small, use e_2 instead. Normalize $\hat{b}_1 := b_{1,\text{proj}} / \|b_{1,\text{proj}}\|$. Rotate \hat{b}_1 about b_3 by ψ_r [5]:

$$b_{1,r} = \cos \psi_r \hat{b}_1 + \sin \psi_r (b_3 \times \hat{b}_1), \quad b_{2,r} = b_3 \times b_{1,r}.$$

Set $R_r = [b_{1,r} \ b_{2,r} \ b_3] \in SO(3)$. Let Ω_r be obtained from flatness (and $\hat{R}_r = R_r \hat{\Omega}_r$, $\hat{\cdot} : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathfrak{so}(3)$).

With $\hat{R} = R \hat{\Omega}$, define

$$R_e := R_r^\top R, \quad \Omega_e := \Omega - R_e^\top \Omega_r.$$

Let $\Omega_u := \text{Log}(R_e)^\vee \in \mathbb{R}^3$ (the matrix logarithm's vee map). For $0 < p_R/q_R < 1$ and $\lambda_R > 0$ define the terminal sliding variable

$$s_R = \Omega_e + \lambda_R |\Omega_u|^{\frac{p_R}{q_R}} \odot \text{sign}(\Omega_u) \in \mathbb{R}^3.$$

We consider a matched torque disturbance $d_\tau(t) \in \mathbb{R}^3$ entering the same channel as M , with $\|d_\tau(t)\| \leq \Delta_\tau$.

Using the geometric equivalent term specialized from (7) with inertia $J \succ 0$,

$$M^{\text{eq}} = (J\Omega) \times (\lambda_R \Omega_u - \eta_R) + J(\dot{\eta}_R - \lambda_R \dot{\Omega}_u), \quad \eta_R := R_e^\top \Omega_r,$$

we adopt a continuous damping and a discontinuous robust term in the same channel:

$$M = M^{\text{eq}} - J K_R s_R - \rho_R J \frac{s_R}{\|s_R\| + \varepsilon}, \quad K_R \succ 0, \quad \rho_R > 0,$$

Let $V_R = \frac{1}{2} \|s_R\|^2$. Substituting M into $J\dot{\Omega} = M - \Omega \times J\Omega + d_\tau$ and using the cancellations in M^{eq} gives the s_R dynamics

$$\dot{s}_R = -K_R s_R - \rho_R \frac{s_R}{\|s_R\| + \varepsilon} + J^{-1} d_\tau.$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}_R &= -s_R^\top K_R s_R - \rho_R \frac{\|s_R\|^2}{\|s_R\| + \varepsilon} + s_R^\top J^{-1} d_\tau \\ &\leq -\lambda_{\min}(K_R) \|s_R\|^2 - \left(\rho_R - \lambda_{\max}(J^{-1}) \Delta_\tau \right) \|s_R\|. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, if $\rho_R > \lambda_{\max}(J^{-1}) \Delta_\tau$, then s_R reaches 0 in finite time and the sliding set is forward invariant despite the matched disturbance; on $s_R = 0$ the reduced error dynamics yield terminal (finite-time) decay via the fractional term.

VII. SIMULATION

We simulate the plant (8) with $m_P = 0.5$ kg, $m_R = 0.85$ kg, $J = I_3$ kg m², $l = 0.45$ m. The initial conditions are $x_0 = [2, 1, 0]^\top$ m, $v_0 = 0$, $\xi_0 = [0, 0, -1]^\top$, $\omega_0 = 0$, $R_0 = I_3$, $\Omega_0 = 0$. The reference is $x_r(t) = [0, 0, -1]^\top + [\cos t, \sin t, -0.2 \cos t]^\top$ (m), with yaw $\psi_r(t) \equiv 0$.

Terminal gains are considered as $\lambda_P = 0.8$, $\lambda_T = 3.2$, $\lambda_R = 100$, while exponents are $p_P/q_P = 70/91$, $p_T/q_T = p_R/q_R = 70/100$. The continuous reaching gains are $K_P = 15$, $K_T = 150$, $K_R = 350$. We select ρ 's from the matched-disturbance bounds derived earlier as: $\rho_P = 20$, $\rho_T = 20$, $\rho_R = 2$, using $\Delta(\cdot) \approx 3\sigma$ from the injected noise and a 20% margin.

We compare against a standard PD+feedforward (PD+FF) controller [6] with gains $k_q = -30$, $k_\omega = -3.2$, $k_R = 800$, $k_\Omega = 40$.

To test robustness, we inject zero-mean Gaussian noise on the thrust and torque channels: $f \leftarrow f + n_f(t)$, $M \leftarrow M + n_M(t)$ with $n_f \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2)$, $n_M \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma^2 I_3)$, $\sigma^2 =$

Fig. 4: Tracking in x (TSMC vs. PD+FF) with injected noise; reference shown in red. (a) TSMC without noise, (b) PD+Feedforward without noise, (c) TSMC with noise, (d) PD+Feedforward with noise.

Fig. 5: 3D path following (TSMC vs. PD+FF) with injected noise; reference shown in red. (a) TSMC without noise, (b) PD+Feedforward without noise, (c) TSMC with noise, (d) PD+Feedforward with noise.

0.5. For the stage-wise robustness conditions, we bound the matched projections by Δ_T, Δ_τ via 3σ .

Figure 4 shows time-series tracking (TSMC vs PD+FF) with and without disturbances while Fig. 5 shows the 3D path. In the disturbance-free case, both controllers track comparably. Under noise, PD+FF exhibits pronounced oscillations and bias in x , while the proposed hierarchical TSMC retains nearly the same tracking as in the nominal case which is consistent with the matched-disturbance rejection guaranteed by the sliding laws. The 3D plot

highlights that TSMC follows the circle reference closely, whereas PD+FF deviates markedly along the thrust-direction changes.

VIII. CONCLUSION

We developed a hierarchical terminal sliding-mode controller (TSMC) for a tethered rigid-body/point-mass system. The dynamics are decomposed into three subsystems: (i) point-mass translation in \mathbb{R}^3 , (ii) tether direction on S^2 using an S^3 lift for curvature-consistent errors, and (iii) rigid-body attitude on $SO(3)$. Each stage applies a terminal sliding variable with continuous reaching term $-Ks$, while a discontinuous bump in the actuated channel ensures finite-time reaching and invariance of the sliding set under bounded disturbances. On the manifold, fractional terms yield finite-time decay of the reduced errors.

Simulations on a reference trajectory show that, while PD+feedforward performs similarly in the disturbance-free case, the proposed hierarchical TSMC maintains tracking quality under injected thrust/torque noise, whereas PD+feedforward degrades significantly. This confirms the robustness predicted by the matched-disturbance analysis. Although we established reaching and finite-time properties for each stage, a complete cascade proof with nontrivial zero dynamics is left for future work.

REFERENCES

- [1] V. I. Utkin, *Sliding modes in control and optimization*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [2] A. Levant, "Sliding order and sliding accuracy in sliding mode control," *International journal of control*, vol. 58, no. 6, pp. 1247–1263, 1993.
- [3] V. Utkin and J. Shi, "Integral sliding mode in systems operating under uncertainty conditions," in *Proceedings of 35th IEEE conference on decision and control*, vol. 4. IEEE, 1996, pp. 4591–4596.
- [4] S. Venkataraman and S. Gulati, "Control of nonlinear systems using terminal sliding modes," 1993.
- [5] S. Tang, K. Sreenath, and V. Kumar, "Aggressive maneuvering of a quadrotor with a cable-suspended payload," in *Robotics: Science and Systems, Workshop on Women in Robotics*. Cite-seer, 2014, pp. 1–20.
- [6] K. Sreenath, T. Lee, and V. Kumar, "Geometric control and differential flatness of a quadrotor uav with a cable-suspended load," in *52nd IEEE conference on decision and control*. IEEE, 2013, pp. 2269–2274.
- [7] G. Yu, D. Cabecinhas, R. Cunha, and C. Silvestre, "Nonlinear backstepping control of a quadrotor-slung load system," *IEEE/ASME Transactions On Mechatronics*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 2304–2315, 2019.
- [8] S. Yang, B. Xian, J. Cai, and G. Wang, "Finite-time convergence control for a quadrotor unmanned aerial vehicle with a slung load," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 605–614, 2023.
- [9] A. Martinez-Vasquez, R. Castro-Linares, and A. E. Rodriguez-Mata, "Sliding mode control of a quadrotor with suspended payload: a differential flatness approach," in *2020 17th International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Computing Science and Automatic Control (CCE)*. IEEE, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [10] F. Ding, C. Sun, Y. Ai, and J. Huang, "Sliding mode control for quadrotor-slung load transportation system with state constraints," in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Cyborg and Bionic Systems (CBS)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 368–373.
- [11] E. Espindola and Y. Tang, "Geometric sliding mode control of mechanical systems on lie groups," *Automatica*, vol. 177, p. 112346, 2025.